

**THE MECHANISM OF FORMATION AND IMPLEMENTATION OF INNOVATIVE
ENTREPRENEURIAL ACTIVITY OF THE LEADING PERSONNEL OF A MODERN
HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTION**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10810440>

Abstract. *It is important to improve the quality of education in higher education institutions in our republic, and to effectively organize scientific and innovative activities. Priority tasks have been defined in the field of development of proposals and recommendations for meaningful and purposeful organization of work on personnel training, retraining, professional development and development of scientific and innovative activities of pedagogues in the higher education system.*

Keywords: *management, personnel staff, professional development, higher education system.*

Entrepreneurial higher education institutions (HEIs) have gained significant traction, both in theory and practice. The concept has evolved from academic entrepreneurship, which gained prominence in the 2000th, into a more comprehensive notion at institutional level and has been an influencing factor for governmental decisions and the region's economic development. This article seeks to present an overview of the evolution of entrepreneurial HEI research and provide a description of the structures characterizing it. This paper presents an in-depth examination and analysis of the current state of research and published literature related to entrepreneurial HEIs.

In the conditions of developing market relations, the problem of the effectiveness of university management is becoming more urgent with the emergence of new demands placed on higher educational institutions by the market of educational services and the labor market, in which a modern educational institution is fully involved. In this regard, to ensure the synergistic effect of the principles of quality management of education at all levels of education in the "2030 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)" adopted at the 70th anniversary session of the United Nations General Assembly, professional interests and needs formation of targeted educational programs was defined as an urgent task.

The current level of development of science, production, technology, technology, public relations is significantly ahead of the quality of education at the university, and thus increases the dependence of the rate of development of society on the level and scope of higher professional education, requires improvement in the use of new forms, methods and principles. This is not only a problem of Uzbekistan, today the initiators and participants of the Bologna process are directed to European higher education, whose main task is to maintain and ensure the necessary quality of the specialist's professional training, and to improve it.

Globalization processes of the economy, the problems of Uzbekistan's integration into the international educational space require solving the issues of systematically ensuring the quality of education in the conditions of universities. Particular emphasis is placed on universities that contribute to the development of industries that require innovative knowledge and, as a result, the national economy of Uzbekistan.

It is important to improve the quality of education in higher education institutions in our republic, and to effectively organize scientific and innovative activities. Priority tasks have been defined in the field of "development of proposals and recommendations for meaningful and

purposeful organization of work on personnel training, retraining, professional development and development of scientific and innovative activities of pedagogues in the higher education system."

Taking into account the above, it is not in vain that we chose the topic of the scientific work as "Mechanism of formation and implementation of innovative entrepreneurial activity of the leading personnel of the modern higher education institution".

Higher education institutions (HEIs) are critical to a society's functioning as they nurture the youth and the future of a nation. According to Guerrero and Urbano¹ (2012), HEIs should ensure that students' interests are aligned with those of the nation's vision. In the last ten years, the role of HEIs has evolved due to national and global factors, resulting in the greater emphasis on developing entrepreneurial HEIs. The key focus here is to produce, not only qualified job seekers, but also develop competent job creators. Practitioners and academics globally have realized that HEIs need to be more effective in dealing with external and internal changes. Following policy changes in the western world, many countries in Asia and Africa have similarly acknowledged the need to change their policies governing HEIs.

An entrepreneurial HEI is an institution that contributes and provides leadership for creating entrepreneurial thinking and one that develops entrepreneurship capital. It has a broader role than just to generate technology transfer in the form of patents, licenses, and start-ups. The concept of entrepreneurial HEIs started to gain traction, both in theory and practice during late 1990s and early 2000s. A significant increase in publications on this topic over the past few years testifies its recognition in the literature. Previous publications indicate the need to better understand the concept at organizational, regional, and global levels. Developments at local and international levels, coupled with the changes in governmental policies identified above have led to more academic institutions concentrating on amalgamating entrepreneurial initiatives and commercialization efforts alongside and embedded with conventional education and research. This has led to the development of numerous research themes in entrepreneurial HEI literature, such as: the development of entrepreneurial mindset and competencies, processes and determinants of student entrepreneurship, researchers engaging in research commercialization activities/academic entrepreneurship (Rasmussen et al., 2014)², and entrepreneurship education (Mathisen & Rasmussen, 2019)³. Hence, to ensure that this field does not fragment further and to support organized generation of further knowledge on entrepreneurial HEIs, it is necessary to understand the structure and extent to which this field has been probed. To address this, an evidence-based roadmap by adopting bibliometric study method is pursued; examining current literature on entrepreneurial HEIs, comparing the emerging research foci and indicating further research avenues; so as to facilitate this field's movement forward.

REFERENCES

1. Guerrero, M., & Urbano, D. (2012). The development of an entrepreneurial university. *Journal of Technology Transfer*, 37(1), 43–74. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10961-010-9171-x>
2. Rasmussen, E., Mosey, S., & Wright, M. (2014). The influence of university departments on the evolution of entrepreneurial competencies in spin-off ventures. *Research Policy*, 43(1), 92–106. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2013.06.007>
3. Mathisen, M. T., & Rasmussen, E. (2019). The development, growth, and performance of university spin-offs: A critical review. *Journal of Technology Transfer*, 44(6), 1891–1938. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10961-018-09714-9>